

action of nitrosyl chloride gas on some of the olefins prompted us to undertake an extension work in cholestane series.

This note reports the syntheses of 3 β ,5 α -dichloro-6 β -nitrocholestane (III) and 5 α -chloro-6 β -nitrocholestane (IV) when nitrosylchloride gas was passed in CCl₄ solution of 3 β -chlorocholest-5-ene (I) and cholest-5-ene (II), respectively at 0°.

Experimental

Nitrosyl chloride gas was prepared by the reported method⁵.

3 β -Chlorocholest-5-ene (I) (2 g) was dissolved in CCl₄ (100 ml) and cooled to 0°. Nitrosyl chloride gas was passed into the solution for 2 h. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in ether and washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and chromatographed over silica gel (40 g). Elution with petroleum ether-ether (40 : 1) gave compound 3 β ,5 α -dichloro-6 β -nitrocholestane (III) (1.5 g), crystallised from methanol, m.p. 111-113° (Found : C, 66.73 ; H, 9.22 ; N, 2.81. C₂₇H₄₅NO₂Cl₂ requires C, 66.80 ; H, 9.27 ; N, 2.88%) ; *m/z* 485/437 (3 : 1) and 439/441 (3 : 1) (M⁺-NO₂) ; ν_{\max} 1555, 1360 (C-NO₂) and 735, 720 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl) ; δ (CDCl₃) 4.7 (dd, C₆- α H, *J* 6.5 Hz and 3.3 Hz, equatorial), 3.9 (mc, C₃- α H, *W*_{1/2} 18Hz, axial, A/B ring junction trans), 2.6 (d, C₄-2H), 1.3 (s, C₁₀-CH₃), 0.78 (s, C₁₃-CH₃), 0.98 and 0.84 (other methyl protons).

Cholest-5-ene (II) (2 g) was dissolved in CCl₄ (100 ml) and cooled to 0°. Nitrosyl chloride gas was allowed to pass into the solution for 2 h. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in ether and washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and chromatographed over silica gel (40 g). Elution with petroleum ether-ether (20 : 1) provided 5 α -chloro-6 β -nitrocholestane (IV) (1.5 g), crystallised from methanol, gave positive Beilstein test, m.p. 91-93° (Found : C, 71.80 ; H, 10.14 ; N, 3.12. C₂₇H₄₅NO₂Cl requires C, 71.84 ; H, 10.20 ; N, 3.10%) ; *m/z* 451/453 (3 : 1) and 405/407 (3 : 1) (M⁺-NO₂) ; ν_{\max} 1553, 1355 (C-NO₂) and 720 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl) ; δ (CDCl₃) 4.6 (dd, C₆- α H, *J* 6.4 Hz and 3.2 Hz, equatorial) 1.25 (s, C₁₀-CH₃), 0.72 (s, C₁₃-CH₃), 0.96 and 0.82 (other methyl protons).

Results and Discussion

The compound (III), m.p. 111-113° was analysed for C₂₇H₄₅NO₂Cl₂. The ir spectrum exhibited bands at 1555, 1360 cm⁻¹ (C-NO₂) and 735, 720 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl). In nmr spectrum signal of C₃-proton appeared at δ 3.9 (*W*_{1/2}, 18 Hz, axial, A/B ring junction trans)⁶. C₆ methine proton appeared at δ 4.7 (dd, *J* 6.5 Hz and 3.3 Hz, equatorial)⁶, therefore, disposition of C-NO₂ bond is axial. A clear doublet at δ 2.6 integrated for two protons is ascribable to C₄-2H. Mass spectrum corroborated the structure, which displayed weak molecular ion peaks at *m/z* 485/487 (3 : 1) and the diagnostic peaks at 439/441 (3 : 1) (M⁺-NO₂).

The compound IV, m.p. 91-93°, gave positive Beilstein test and analysed for C₂₇H₄₅NO₂Cl. The ir spectrum showed bands at 1553, 1355 (C-NO₂) and 720 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl). The nmr spectrum displayed a double doublet at δ 4.6 integrated for one proton (*J* 6.4 Hz and 3.2 Hz) ascribable to C₆- α H (equatorial). The structure was confirmed by mass spectrum which exhibited molecular ion peaks at *m/z* 451/453 (3 : 1) and 405/407 (3 : 1) (M⁺-NO₂).

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Hentriacontan-12-ol and Other Waxy Constituents of *Tamarix gallica* Linn.**

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TAMARIX gallica Linn. (Syn. *Tamarix troupil* Hole) commonly called *Jhau* belongs to family Tamaricaceae and is used in various ailments in Ayurvedic

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NOTES

system of medicine^{1,2}. Previously only 3,3'-dimethyl-ether of ellagic acid³, polyphenols⁴, and phytosterols⁵ have been isolated. In view of its medicinal values, a chemical study of the aerial parts of this shrub was undertaken and reported in this paper.

Results and Discussion

The aerial parts of *Tamarix gallica* Linn (900 g) after drying in air was ground and extracted thrice with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) under reflux for 36 h. A dark greenish semi-solid extract (1.0%) was obtained which was neutral to universal indicator. The extract after usual workup was subjected to column chromatographic separation over activated alumina (40 fold excess) which gave different waxy fractions.

Fraction A: Elution with petroleum-ether (b.p. 60-80°) gave a waxy fraction (1.72 g) which showed two spots on tlc (silica gel, 2% AgNO₃) and therefore, was further resolved on a column of silica gel impregnated with 15% AgNO₃ and deactivated with 8% of water. Elution of the column with n-hexane and petroleum ether gave two products, respectively (Rf 1.0 and 0.87).

Product A: Hexane eluate on crystallisation from acetone-alcohol gave a waxy product (0.053 g), m.p. 53-55°. Its ir spectrum indicated the presence of alkanes with a long chain. It represented according to glc analysis the homologous series of n-alkanes C₁₈-C₃₅ (Table 1) with a maximum occurrence of n-hentriacontane (C₃₁, 25.21%), n-nonacosane (C₂₉, 14.68%) and n-heptacosane (C₂₇, 15.87%). Odd numbered homologue predominated over the even ones^{6,7}. The distribution pattern of n-alkanes has been found to be of unimodal type⁸.

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION OF n-ALKANES*

Sl. no.	No. of C-atoms	%
1	C ₁₈	traces
2	C ₁₉	0.10
3	C ₂₀	0.41
4	C ₂₁	0.62
5	C ₂₂	1.05
6	C ₂₃	1.54
7	C ₂₄	2.09
8	C ₂₅	3.81
9	C ₂₆	8.24
10	C ₂₇	15.87
11	C ₂₈	9.47
12	C ₂₉	14.68
13	C ₃₀	6.81
14	C ₃₁	25.21
15	C ₃₂	5.07
16	C ₃₃	4.59
17	C ₃₄	0.98
18	C ₃₅	0.25

* Glc analysis.

Product B: The second product was found of esters which showed prominent ir bands at 1170, 1735 cm⁻¹. This product was then analysed by glc

which represented the homologous series of long chain esters (C₄₀-C₅₂) (Table 2) with a maximum occurrence of C₄₄ ester (32%). Even numbered esters were prevailing. However, odd numbered esters were also found in traces. The actual composition of fatty acids and alcohols in natural esters was not determined but according to results published earlier^{9,10}, it is supposed that single chromatographic peaks do not represent individual substances but mixtures of esters.

TABLE 2—COMPOSITION OF ESTERS*

Sl. no.	No. of C-atoms	%
1	C ₄₀	3
2	C ₄₂	5
3	C ₄₄	32
4	C ₄₆	17
5	C ₄₈	19
6	C ₅₀	5
7	C ₅₂	3
8	unidentified	16

* Glc analysis.

Fraction B: Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (3:1) gave the fraction of secondary alcohols (0.196 g) which showed ir spectrum peaks at 1022, 1047, 1110, 1125, 1330 cm⁻¹. It was analysed by combined gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). The secondary alcohol consisted almost entirely of 12-hydroxy-hentriacontane (97%) with 1% each of C₂₉ and C₃₃ mixtures of homologue. C₂₉ secondary alcohol has been found to be a mixture of 12-OH and 10-OH isomers showing characteristic mass fragmentation peaks at m/e 496 (M⁺), 257 and 341 (12-OH isomer), 229 and 269 (10-OH isomer). C₃₃ secondary alcohol has been composed of 12-OH and 14-OH isomers showing characteristic mass fragmentation peaks at m/e 552 (M⁺), 257 and 397 (12-OH isomer), 285 and 369 (14-OH isomer).

It is worth mentioning here that the higher content of hentriacontan-12-OH, 97% of the total secondary alcohols, is unique findings in plants. Isolation of this unsymmetrical secondary alcohol has previously been reported only in *Fragaria* sp.¹¹, in which ca. 25% of 12-OH isomer was found in the mixture of secondary alcohols.

Fraction C: Further elution with petroleum ether-benzene (1:3) gave another fraction on crystallisation from methanol (0.1730 g), m.p. 84-85° and tlc homogeneous. The peaks in ir spectrum showed it an aliphatic long chain primary alcohol. It exhibited in mass spectrum the significant ions at m/e 438 (M⁺), 437 (M⁺-1), 420 (M⁺-H₂O), 392 [M⁺-(olefin+H₂O)], 45, 59, 73, 87 etc. Thus the primary alcohol was identified as n-triacontanol on the above basis and by preparation of its acetyl derivative, m.p. 67-68° (lit.¹² 69°). It was further confirmed when compared with the authentic specimen (co-tlc, m.m.p.).

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The Application of *p*-Amino-*o*,*o'*-dimethylazobenzene as Adsorption Indicator in Argentometry of Halides and Thiocyanate

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AS an extension of our earlier studies¹⁻³ investigations on the application of *p*-amino-*o*,*o'*-azobenzene in precipitometry of halides (Cl⁻, Br⁻ and I⁻) and thiocyanate (SCN⁻) using silver nitrate, have been made. The results of these investigations are presented in this communication.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R., B.D.H. or G.R., E. Merck grade. Stock solutions of halides, thiocyanate and silver nitrate were prepared in double-distilled water and standardised by usual

methods. 0.2% solution of the dye was used (2-4 drops) as the indicator. The detailed experimental procedure has been described in our earlier communication¹.

In the argentometry of halides and thiocyanate, *p*-amino-*o*,*o'*-azobenzene dye is found to exhibit a sharp colour change from pink to yellow in the pH range 2-4.5. The indicator responded equally well in the reverse titration (Ag⁺ vs halides) with a colour change from yellow to pink at the end point. The results are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—TITRATIONS OF HALIDES AND THIOCYANATE USING *p*-AMINO-*o*,*o'*-DIMETHYL AZOBENZENE AS ADSORPTION INDICATOR WITH Ag⁺ IONS*

Vol. of halide solution taken = 10.00 ml	
Concn. of halide/pseudohalide <i>M</i>	Vol. (ml), Concn. (<i>M</i>) of AgNO ₃
0.1 KCl/KI	9.98-10.00, 0.1
0.1 KBr/KSCN	10.00-10.02, 0.1
0.01 KCl/KBr	10.00, 0.02
0.02 KSCN/KI	9.98-10.00, 0.02
0.01 KCl/KBr	9.98-10.02, 0.01
0.01 KI/KSCN	10.00-10.02, 0.01

* Titrations were conducted in presence of 2.0-4.0 ml 0.01 *M* HNO₃. The colour change yellow to pink was sharp and reversible. Coagulation of Ag-halide/thiocyanate occurred just at the end point.

TABLE 2—TITRATIONS OF Ag⁺ IONS USING *p*-AMINO-*o*,*o'*-DIMETHYL AZOBENZENE AS INDICATOR WITH HALIDE/THIOCYANATE IONS*

Vol. of AgNO ₃ taken = 10.00 ml	
Concn. of AgNO ₃ <i>M</i>	Vol. (ml), Concn. (<i>M</i>) halide/pseudohalide
0.1	9.98-10.00, 0.1 KCl/KSCN
0.1	10.00-10.02, 0.1 KBr/KI
0.02	10.00, 0.02 KCl/KSCN
0.02	10.00-10.02, 0.02 KBr/KI
0.01	9.98-10.00, 0.01 KCl/KBr
0.01	10.00-10.02, 0.01 KI/KSCN

* Titrations were performed in presence of 2.5-4.5 ml 0.01 *M* HNO₃. Coagulation of Ag-halide/thiocyanate occurred earlier and dye adsorbed on the coagulated particles, but at equivalence point desorption of the dye starts. Changes are sharp and reversible.

Determination of iodide in a mixture of chloride and iodide: The titration of iodide in a mixture of chloride and iodide was carried out using *p*-amino-*o*,*o'*-azobenzene. The mixtures containing varying concentration were taken. The solution was adjusted to pH 4 by adding requisite amount of 0.1 *M* HNO₃. Four drops of the dye solution were added to the solution which was titrated against standard solution of silver nitrate. At that pH only iodide was titrated and the results are shown in Table 3.